

IPAD-MD Expert Group Meeting on Data & Resources

Deliverable 7.5 (WP7)

Meeting Report on INFRAFRONTIER Workshop on Sustainability of Mouse Informatics Resources

September 25rd – 26th, 2019
Strasbourg, France

Reported by:
Dr. Asrar Ali Khan and Dr. Michael Raess

The IPAD-MD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 653961

Table of Contents:

Introduction	1
<i>Objectives</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Workshop Structure</i>	<i>2</i>
Agenda	3
Workshop Overview	5
<i>Workshop Talks</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>Panel Discussion</i>	<i>10</i>
Concluding Remarks and Outcome	13

Introduction

Mouse informatics resources are invaluable and essential for life sciences research. The continuous availability of these resources is crucial for the global biomedical research community.

With the National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI) cutting funding for model organism databases and subsequent merger of Mouse Genome Informatics (MGI) with other model organism databases to form the Alliance of Genomic Resources (AGR) - the question of long-term sustainability of these resources has again gained visibility among different user groups of these resources and other stakeholders. How to develop them further to meet the latest needs of the research community and make them 'future-proof', is an important endeavour for researchers and funders worldwide.

The INFRAFRONTIER workshop aimed to openly discuss the status quo of international mouse informatics resources (like MGI and IMSR) and the strategic plans of major mouse data providers and repositories like IMPC, RIKEN, EMMA, MMRRC etc. The workshop talks were attended by 25 participants and experts from leading mouse repositories and informatics resources in Europe, North America and Asia presented their tools, approaches, and ideas for improving sustainability like cloud storage and open data policies, machine learning for automated curation and ongoing international cooperation. This workshop was organised by INFRAFRONTIER as milestone M17 for the IPAD-MD project (grant agreement No. 653961) under WP7 – Access to Data and Resources.

Objectives

The objectives of the workshop were to discuss:

- Strategic plans of the major international mouse data providers and repositories
- Current challenges for the sustainability of mouse informatics resources
- Sustainability funding opportunities and models
- Collaborative opportunities between the international mouse repositories

- Innovations concerning the access to mouse informatics resources, cloud data storage, machine learning etc.

Workshop Structure

25 September 2019 09:00 - 12:00: Workshop Talks

26 September 2019 17:15 - 18:15: Panel Discussion

The workshop was organised as an INFRAFRONTIER satellite event at the International Mammalian Genome Conference 2019 in Strasbourg.

The workshop talks and discussions were scheduled on the morning of 25th September along with the other IMGCC workshops and was attended by 25 participants. The panel discussion (PD) took place on the following afternoon on 26th September to accommodate the attendance of Dr. Carol Bult from The Jackson Laboratory and to involve the IMGCC 2019 conference participants in the panel discussion.

Speakers and Panelists:

Carol Bult	Jackson Laboratory, MGI	Speaker and panelist
Sabine Fessele	INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure	Speaker
John Hancock	ELIXIR Research Infrastructure	Speaker and panelist
Anne Kwitek	Rat Genome Database	Speaker and panelist
Kent Lloyd	UC Davis, MMRRC	Speaker and PD chair
Terry Meehan	EMBL-EBI	Speaker and panelist
Michael Raess	INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure	Speaker and panelist
Atsushi Yoshiki	RIKEN BioResource Research Center	Speaker and panelist

Agenda

Venue: IGBMC, 1 rue Laurent Fries, Parc d'Innovation, 67404 Strasbourg-IIIkirch

25th September, Wednesday (Room iCS 3013)

09:00 – 09:20 Sabine Fessele – INFRAFRONTIER and EMMA

09:20 – 09:40 Kent Lloyd – Mutant Mouse Resource and Research Centers (MMRRC)

09:40 – 10:00 Anne Kwitek – Rat Genome Database (RGD)

10:00 – 10:20 John Hancock – ELIXIR UK

10:20 – 10:45 Coffee Break

10:45 – 11:05 Terry Meehan – EMBL-EBI

11:05 – 11:25 Atsushi Yoshiki – RIKEN BioResource Research Center

11:25 – 12:30 General Discussion

18:30 – 20:30 IMGC 2019 Cocktail reception and dinner

26th September, Thursday (main conference hall)

15:15 – 17:15 IMGC Poster session and coffee break

17:15 – 18:15 Panel Discussion chaired by Kent Lloyd:

- Carol Bult
- Michael Raess
- Anne Kwitek
- Terry Meehan
- Atsushi Yoshiki
- John Hancock

Panel discussion at IMGc 2019

Group talks and group discussion on day 1

Workshop Overview

Workshop Talks

Introduction by Dr. Michael Raess

Dr. Raess started off the workshop with a brief introduction of INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC and classified the different mouse repositories and informatics resources present at the workshop as physical resources, data providers, data aggregators and bioinformatics resources (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Classification of different mouse (and rat) repositories and informatics resources presented by Dr. Michael Raess

Dr. Raess also briefly mentioned some of the technologies (like CRISPR-Cas genome editing and machine learning) and policies measures (like merger of model organism databases and open science policies) that could affect sustainability of these repositories and resources.

Sabine Fessele – INFRAFRONTIER and EMMA

Dr. Sabine Fessele presented INFRAFRONTIER role as a mouse data resource that aggregates data produced by the European nodes. She also presented INFRAFRONTIER's interaction with MGI and IMSR as an important avenue of sustainability (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The interaction of INFRAFRONTIER with MGI and IMSR regarding mouse data.

Kent Lloyd – Mutant Mouse Resource and Research Centers (MMRRC)

Dr. Kent Lloyd from the MMRRC started off by saying that mouse repositories like MMRRC and EMMA play a role in adding value and important information to the genetic and phenotyping mouse strain data which are transferred on to mouse informatics resources. He also briefly explained the general operational principles of mouse repositories like providing world-wide access to mouse strains, increasing awareness of available mouse strains, providing technical support to users etc. and stated that there is strong interdependence of physical (mice) and digital (data) resources due to a bi-directional flow of information that is

essential to the success and sustainability of both. Dr. Kent also highlighted some of the different kinds sustainability challenges faced by mouse repositories like the adoption and utilisation of services (disproportionate demand for mouse lines, CRISPR-Cas9 technology etc.), community challenges (coordination and integration, shared best-practices etc.), funding and limited resources (reproducibility, high variety of alleles etc.) and some additional challenges like the commitment and investment of parent institutes towards services that will primarily be used by external users and tepid engagements by journals and funders in enforcing the inclusion of mouse strains details and sources in articles and grants. On the other side of the coin, several developments have increased the importance of mouse repositories such as the widespread focus on reproducibility and the need to validate *in vitro* model systems like organs-on-a-chip, organoids in *in vivo* models.

Anne Kwitek – Rat Genome Database (RGD)

Dr. Anne Kwitek presented about the Rat Genome Database as an integrated multispecies data resource with goal to introduce data resources at RGD. RGD is not only a database for rat models but a cross-species database that enables researchers to navigate phenotypes and genotypes across different model organisms. Dr. Kwitek presented a demo to identify new deafness models with a focus on cross-species integration that links to MGI and AGR.

John Hancock – ELIXIR UK

Dr. John Hancock the Communities Coordinator for ELIXIR presented about 'ELIXIR, Communities and Sustainability'. After brief introduction about ELIXIR that included its members and observers, five shared data-related service platforms, and ELIXIR Communities, Dr. Hancock spoke about the ELIXIR Data Platform and its mission to drive long-term sustainability of life science data resources. He also mentioned ELIXIR's participation in the international Global Biodata Coalition (GBC) that ensures collective support for crucial data resources essential to the work of life science researchers, educators, and innovators worldwide. To design and implement an international plan for long-term data resources sustainability, it's important to determine which data resources are of fundamental importance and are also eligible for shared international support. This led back to the GBC that essentially aims to establish a funders coalition consisting of as many international biomedical and life sciences funding bodies as possible, which would

provide global coordination and enhancement of up to 100 designated core data resources.

Dr. Hancock ended with the following points:

- The GBC is about stimulating coordination amongst global funders to provide sustainable funding
 - It concentrates on the data resource landscape with focus on Core Data Resources
 - There are issues of scalability and what needs to be sustained
- Neither ELIXIR nor GBC are explicitly about providing infrastructure services e.g. computing resources for data preservation free from ELIXIR
- There is a need for infrastructure for preserving valuable datasets
 - Recommended Deposition Databases
 - BioStudies @ EBI
- There is potential to establish deeper interactions with ELIXIR via a new Community or Task Force (eg. rare diseases)
- Being a part of ELIXIR improves the sustainability aspects of the data sets because of its national and third-party funding models and its association to EMBL

Terry Meehan – EMBL-EBI

Dr. Terry Meehan the coordinator for mouse informatics at EMBL-EBI started off by describing the different types of funding sources important for sustainability of resources and their pros and cons. For e.g., structural funding offers long-term sustainability and allows open data policies but can be perceived to compete with traditional research funding. Institutional funding on the other hand is also sustainable, is closer to researchers and can also involve open data but with additional challenges to get institutes to commit, view the resource as a revenue source and duplication with other resources. The life cycle of data resources consists of investment, development, operational and transitional. The transitional phase has an important sustainability aspect to it because issues related to scaling and security, users need and technological evolution and funding policy changes invariably arise during the lifetime of a data resource. This phase is also very challenging as it involves changes to and migration of the data resource that ideally but unfortunately not always, includes the separation of the infrastructure (like the database, informatics technologies etc.) from the actual data. Some of the successful transitions of bioinformatics

resources include the new IMPC website (www.mousephenotyping.org), the formation of the Alliance of Genome Resources and the evolution of The Arabidopsis Information Resource (TAIR) to a paid subscription model. The TAIR paid subscription model was extensively discussed and was decided to be brought up again at the panel discussion for feedback from the conference participants.

Atsushi Yoshiki – RIKEN BioResource Research Center

Dr. Atsushi Yoshiki and Dr. Hiroshi Masuya from the Experimental Animal Division and Integrated Bioresource Informatics Division (RIKEN BioResource Center, Japan) gave an update about their mouse resources and informatics division, respectively. Dr. Yoshiki started with a brief introduction of the RIKEN BioResource Center and the National BioResource Project (NBRP) that distributes 200 – 300 mouse strains per year and has an archive of 8,950 strains. Dr. Yoshiki also highlighted some of the strains created in Japan, the stringent quality control testing, user publications and RIKEN's participation in the IMPC. Dr. Masuya presented the challenges involved in the establishment of a sustainable informatics infrastructure for a bioresource. The Integrated Bioresource Information Division was established to improve sustainability and for dissemination, sharing and analysis of data. One means towards these goals is the adoption of data standards. This entails that:

- Improvement of reusability and interoperability of data will secure sustainable use of software applications
- Capability of decentralized operation may also secure sustainability
- Collaboration based on common technologies reduces cost for development of data and software application
- As the infrastructure of life science, bioresource information should be standardized

The following changes at the hardware level are underway to increase sustainability:

- Sharing computer resources that reduces total cost
- Remote backup in collaboration with remote labs
- For cloud computing, balance of reliability, performance and cost should be considered

Panel Discussion

The panel discussion started with a quick introduction of the topic and panelists by Dr. Kent Lloyd who chaired the session. Dr. Michael Raess presented a brief recap of the talks and group discussions from the previous workshop session. Before the panel discussion, Prof. Dr. Carol Bult (The Jackson Laboratory), Program Director for Mouse Genome Database (MGD) gave an informative talk on the sustainability of this database, the largest mouse informatics resources in the world, and its incorporation into the Alliance for Genome Resources. Prof. Bult presented key points that are important to a bioinformatics database sustainability strategy (in relation to the various databases at The Jackson Laboratory). These include:

- Leverage and collaboration: MGI is a collection of different databases (eg. MGD, GXD, MMHCdb, IMSR, MouseMine, Gene Ontology) that share specialized infrastructure and expertise adding to its sustainability. It also collaborates with various research groups around the world on different components of the database making effective use of limited resources.
- Diversity of funding: Different grants fund different database components within MGI.
- Prioritisation: Focus on unique value-adding contributions like harmonisation of the nomenclature - mouse genes, alleles and strains (working with the International Committee on Standardized Genetic Nomenclature for Mice), functional annotation of mouse genes (Gene Ontology) etc.
- Efficiency and scalability: Semi-automated curation processes for routine cases with manual curation focusing on difficult cases.
- Modernisation of the data ecosystem: The Alliance of Genome Resources (AGR) is an example of a “knowledge commons” approach to shared infrastructure with a framework that encourages collaboration. It consists of 2 components – the Alliance Central and the Alliance Knowledge Centers.
 - Alliance Central: This component houses the infrastructure needed to run the model organism databases and is directly funded by the NHGRI. The idea behind this component is ‘develop once and used by all’. For e.g., a particular interface or widget that deals with a common type of data can be used by all

model organism databases for this data. Cloud based data storage options are also being explored but involve substantial costs at the moment.

- Knowledge Centers: This component comprises of the individual model organism expertise that work to harmonise representation of concepts across the models for e.g., phenotype and disease models among the different organisms.
- AGR is a good model of sustainability from the ‘develop once and used by all’ standpoint but organism-specific curation is still a necessity and a cost-intensive activity.

Dr. Kent started the panel discussion after Prof. Bult’s talk. This session can be distilled down to the following main points:

- The database includes biological data and relevant technology, and informatics that involves processing of the data, annotation and standardisation are both important resources and cannot exist independently. The database structure changes with the evolution of tools and technology and the scientific question being investigated or presented. However, the aggregation of information from different heterogeneous sources and presenting it to the users in an operable form will always be needed and will need to be adapted.
- The need for model organism-specific data curation, annotation and standardisation will always be important in the context of cooperative resources like AGR. The Alliance Central part of AGR only provides the common infrastructure to ensure that users have a uniform experience when exploring the different model organism data. Therefore, the sustainability of these model organism specific-bioinformatic processes is still a pressing issue.
- There is a close symbiotic relationship between mouse informatics resources and repositories in terms of adding value to their respective services that ultimately benefits the wider user community. Repositories provide genotyping and phenotyping data to informatics resources while the informatics resources in turn provide repositories with access to new users searching for specific mouse strains as well as rich literature-curated strain specific information back to the repositories.

- A subscription-based model for access to informatics resources was met with poor support. The following objections were put forward:
 - This model will close off access to a substantial number of users worldwide.
 - It will prevent seamless integration of data into other tools and services because on restriction on aggregating different free and paid data sets.
 - Users that contribute to datasets will expect to have it freely available to everyone.
- It was suggested to look for funding models outside the scientific community. For e.g., a small lead generation fee can be added to users ordering mouse strains off of repositories. This fee can go into sustaining the informatics resources that made it possible to find the correct strain.
- Funding agencies can include a data stewardship tax on grants for large-scale big data research projects that generate enormous amounts of data. This would go towards the downstream maintenance of the data and making it ‘research-ready’, available and accessible.
- At least in the NIH, different institutes can share the cost of maintaining informatics resources because they are routinely used by their constituents.
- The Global Biodata Coalition will most likely play an important part in the future towards mouse informatics sustainability as it’s an international initiative that coordinates funding of life sciences data resources.
- The issue of sustainability also needs to be addressed at a higher level i.e. at the level of mouse research and resources. The direct connection in to the relevance of mouse and animal models into the human condition needs to be made obvious by presenting more opportunities to involve clinicians and human geneticists. To this end, IPAD-MD will organise a workshop at the AHSG 2019 on the data integration for rare diseases between human geneticists and mouse researchers (M18, D&R Expert Group Meeting VI).
- In the case of mouse repositories, the International Mouse Genome Society (IMGS) accurately cite the source of the mouse strain used in their research. This is however, not common outside the IMGS community. Researchers need to be made aware that inadequate or incorrect references to the mouse strain source will affect the sustainability of mouse repositories.

- The above point is also true mouse informatics resources. Most researchers cite a general bioinformatics resource like NCBI as a source of their mouse genetic information like annotations data but do not cite the actual source (eg. MGD). Again, researchers need to be aware for the need for proper bioinformatic citations. Similarly, the use of these resources also needs to be explicitly stated in grant applications.
- Funding agencies should treat mouse informatics resources as important biomedical infrastructures because of their widespread usage and constant growth and development. As a result, suitable infrastructure-grants should be made available to them.

Concluding Remarks and Outcome

Representatives from prominent mouse repositories and informatics resources attended this workshop on the sustainability of mouse informatics resources and presented comprehensive overviews about their respective resource. Although the focus was on informatics resources, it was clear that mouse repositories and informatics resources function in a close symbiosis and sustainability of one will affect the other. The topic was of prime interest to the participants and was met with enthusiastic discussion at every stage.

Several sustainability challenges faced by these resources and repositories were brought up like the adoption and utilisation of new technology (e.g. CRISPR-Cas9), limited funding and imprecise or lack of citations for these resources during publication. Different measures were also mentioned to solve these issues like data standardisation and efficiency and scalability (like semi-automated curation). Cloud based databases are also a promising solution but at the moment are expensive and might require data access fees. Alternate funding models were also talked about like the data stewardship tax and research infrastructure grants.

A prominent use case solution for dealing with bioinformatics sustainability was the Alliance of Genome Resources – a model organism database merger. The effect on sustainability via its ‘build once and used by all’ infrastructure model was presented and

the importance for organism-specific curation was highlighted in this setting. The Global Biodata Coalition was introduced as an interesting avenue to improve sustainability in the future. The importance of transitions in the life cycle of bioinformatics resources was explained with successful (TAIR) and unsuccessful cases (Sanger's mouse transgenic unit).

The workshop was comprehensive and rose awareness in a wide range of topics relating to the sustainability of mouse informatics resources that included challenges, solutions and upcoming international policies.